

“Let's start over”: How does Wong Kar-Wai's *Happy Together* (1997) impact Hong Kong's queer history

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the influence of Wong Kar-Wai's *Happy Together* (1997) on the queer history of Hong Kong, highlighting its dual representation as a narrative centered on loneliness and as a culturally significant portrayal of queer themes. Wong Kar-Wai maintains that the film is not explicitly queer; however, its depiction of the turbulent relationship between the two gay protagonists, Lai Yiu-Fai and Ho Po-Wing, engages with broader societal dialogues concerning queerness and isolation. This study employs Alexander Doty's conceptualization of queerness in conjunction with psychoanalytic theories from Freud and Lacan to deconstruct the film's representation of love, power dynamics, and recurrent trauma. Contextualizing the film's release within the complicated socio-political landscape of 1990s Hong Kong, the analysis reveals how *Happy Together* transcends its narrative intent, emerging as a cultural touchstone that contributes to the normalization of LGBTQ+ identities. Furthermore, comparisons with Wong Kar-Wai's *ChungKing Express* (1994) and *In the Mood for Love* (2000) illuminate the universal themes of love and heartbreak present in his oeuvre, which transcends issues of gender and sexual orientation. Ultimately, this paper positions *Happy Together* as a significant contribution to both cinematic and social discourses, reflecting the common humanity shared in both queer and non-queer experiences.

1. Is there something queer here?

In, *Happy Together* (1997), the two protagonists have a homosexual romance but, does their romance make the film queer?

To understand if the film itself is queer, we need to define what does make something queer. In scholar Alexander Doty's book chapter, "*There's Something Queer Here*" of his book, *Making Things Perfectly Queer: Interpreting Mass Culture* (1993) they argue the term "queerness" is a mass culture reception practice that is shared by all types of people in different degrees of intensity (Doty, 1993, p.2).

1.1 The meaning of queer

Doty coined the term "queer", to refer to something ambiguous, as they wanted to describe something with a wide range of impulses and cultural expressions that also included transexual, bisexual and straight queerness (Doty, 1993, p.2).

In Doty's opinion, the "queer" "is to stand outside the relatively clear-cut and essentializing categories of sexual identity under which most people function." (Doty, 1993, p.15)

Doty cites scholar Sue-Ellen Case, as she points out that unlike lesbian or gay theory, queer is not gender specific as she follow this by saying that both theories, gay and lesbian do reinscribe sexual difference but only up to some extent as they do it from their specific genre and sexual orientation constructs (Sue-Ellen Case as cited in Doty, 2013, p.5) In addition to Ellen Case's argument, Doty claims that:

"The understanding of what "gender" is in these cases can range from accepting conventional straight forms, which naturalize "feminine" and "masculine" by conflating them with essentializing, biology-based conceptions of "woman" and "man"; to imitating the outward forms and behaviors of one gender or the other while not fully subscribing to the straight ideological imperatives that define that gender; to

combining or ignoring traditional gender codes in order to reflect attitudes that have little or nothing to do with straight ideas about femininity/women or masculinity/men. These last two positions are the places where queerly reconfigured gender identity begin to be worked out”(Doty,2013, p.5)

So what we can conclude is, that queerness is something that stands completely outside of categories of sexual identity, as it is something that can range from conventional straight forms to not accepting any normative ideas of feminity and masculinity.

1.2 Happy Together: A queer film?

But how does this apply to our case of study? As we said before, *Happy Together* (1997) is a film where the two main protagonists are two male young adults that have a homosexual romantic relationship. *Happy Together* (1997) is a film that, in the words of Jiaying Sim, invokes new modes and non-normative models of thinking about queer identification and representation (Sim,2021, p.416). In Sim’s opinion, “Happy Together calls for new ways of thinking about queer desire as relationality that manifests through the power of sensations” (Sim,2021, p.423).

On the contrary to Sim’s argument, it is necessary to point out that this statement might not be entirely true as, in the words of Ching-Yi Chung, *Happy Together* (1997) is a movie that is about the loneliness of the human condition, being a film that is not so much about a failed homosexual relationship, but is more about the selfish and sophistic nature that makes us humans beings, unable to transcend ourselves to loving genuinely (Chung,2013,p.8). In addition, Wong Kar-Wai himself argued that the film is not a gay film but more about being alone with someone else.

Moreover, scholar Jeremy Tambling argues that the film is affirmative on representing homosexuality because it is represented on the film but it does not bother to discuss about it, making the relationship not stand out, but actually being no different from any other sexual

partnership, being more centered around, not only as we previously said about learning to be with yourself , but also to learn to be happy with yourself and your past (Tambling,2003, p.69).

It is dangerous to affirm both that *Happy Together* is a queer film and, that *Happy Together* is not a queer film, as its queerness runs through different planes, being a narrational one, based on the film itself and, the other one being the social one that reflects the impact that the movie has on society.

To clarify our argument, the film can be both queer and not queer at the same time as, in the aspect of the movie itself, we have seen that is not a queer movie itself, as the relationship between Ho and Fai relies more on other topics like learning about loneliness and accepting your past and no so much on queer themes itself but, on the other hand, the film is queer in social terms, because of the social impact the film possess. When arguing about what is to be queer, we can see that queerness is something that can range from straight accepting normative canons to completely denying them and this film by portraying two gay characters, makes the easy for homosexual gay men to empathize with it more than any other gender and sexually oriented category.

The conclusion for this first chapter, would be that *Happy Together* (1997) can be both a queer film or not, depending on the type of perspective you want to apply to the movie as, if you do it from a narrative and filmic point of view, it is like Wong Kar-Wai argued, that is not a gay movie but, if we look it from a social point of view it can apply to queer thematics.

From social terms, the film is important to queer history, specifically to Hong Kong's queer history, which is the next topic we are going to discuss.

2. 1990s Hong Kong Queer History

“Sexual orientation and gender identity have long been regarded as sensitive subjects in Hong Kong and the attitudes towards, and experiences of, lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender

(LGBT) individuals are not widely understood.”(Vernon & Yik, 2012, p.4) which is why to explain the context in which *Happy Together* (1997) was released we will look at what was the situation of queer individuals in 1990s Hong Kong.

2.1 *Tongzhi* movement and homosexuality in Hong Kong

To contextualize the situation, we will discuss the movement of *tongzhi*, which according to scholars Travis Kong, Sky Lau and Eva Li on “*The fourth wave? A critical reflection of the tongzhi movement in Hong Kong*” (2015), it means “common will”, being an adaptation of the Chinese term “comrade” (Kong et al.,2015,p.188).

In the 1980s, this movement tried to conduct a based claim that homosexuals should have the right to have sex in private but, few gay men openly came out to fight for their rights (Kong et al.,2015, p.192). Fear of speaking up was a common thing that happened throughout the last decades of Hong Kong’s history.

According to scholars Yiu Tung Suen and Miu Yin Wong on their book chapter Male “*Homosexuality in Hong Kong: A 20-Year Review of Public Attitudes Towards Homosexuality and Experiences of Discrimination Self- Reported by Gay Men*”(2017) “A review of existing studies on public attitudes towards homosexuality in Hong Kong reveals that homosexuals in Hong Kong are living in a social environment ridden with negative conceptions about them (Suen & Wong,2017, p.73).

This negative connotation, radiates from different aspects like education where homosexuality is treated as an “immoral and sinful practice is commonly taught in formal and informal curricula in schools in Hong Kong, which creates an unfriendly atmosphere for gay students.”(Suen & Wong,2017, p.75).

Apart from education, family was a big problem when coming out as queer, which also influenced that in the 1980s very few gay men came out to fight for their rights as:

“Traditional Chinese culture, which emphasizes family values, conforming to traditional gender and family roles, and the production of off - spring to continue the family name, are still influential in Hong Kong.” (Suen and Wong,2017, p.78)

When talking about family, scholars Kate Vernon and Amanda Yik did a study on titled “*Hong Kong LGBT Climate Study 2011-12 Attitudes to and experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender employees*” (2012), where they analyzed that there where three main reasons on LGBT employees did not come out to their families as a 66% argued that their family may not understand them, a 63% claimed that they might not be accepted and a 38% said that they where afraid of their families being ashamed of them (Vernon & Yik, 2012, p.23).

2.2 1997’s Hong Kong: From the UK to China

It is by comparing a study from 2012 and a study of 1996, that the situation in 1990s Hong Kong’s society was worse as Suen and Wong cite the Home Affairs Branch study titled “*A consultation paper: Equal opportunities - A study on discrimination on the ground of sexual orientation.*”(1996) where a majority of the public held negative attitudes towards homosexuals with a score of 3.4 out of 10, being the majority of the population opposed to any legislation that could protect homosexuals in Hong Kong (Home Affairs Branch,1996 as cited in Suen & Wong,2017, p.74).

The year 1997, could be described as the last year of what Kong et al. (2015) argue on their paper “*The second wave (1991-97): Governance-in-transition, tongzhi identity, community building and assimilationist tongzhi politics*” where they talk about once the decriminalization of homosexual conduct was over, as it transformed into arguments of social and moral disputes where different parties started to divide themselves between “pro-gay” and “anti-gay”, creating social conflicts such as Chinese tradition vs Western culture or heterosexuality vs homosexuality (Kong et al.,2015, p.192)

Having said this and by looking at the context we have discussed, we can take into justify Lim's (2002) argument that "Hong Kong's imminent return to China acted as an impetus for the representation of homosexuality in Hong Kong cinema"(Lim,2002, p.79) as the fear of censorship system haunted film directors it was when many filmmakers rushed to complete their films before China's arrival, same can be attributed to Wong Kar-Wai (Lim,2002, p.79) as in *Happy Together* (1997), there are small references to Hong Kong's political and homosexual views that we will be later discussed.

In conclusion, we can see that *Happy Together* premiered at a very controversial time where Hong Kong's film industry faced censorship and where many queer individuals struggled with their identities, being threatened and assaulted for their queerness.

Is it because of these reasons, that we can see how the film impacted queer history in Hong Kong, by talking openly about homosexuality as Tambling argues "One argument runs that the film is not about homosexuality at all, that it is just about relationships, which happen to be homosexual, but could easily be heterosexual" (Tambling,2003, p.69) therefore creating a sense of identification for all queer and non-queer individuals.

In the next part of our research, we will look into Wong Kar-Wai's cinema by looking at how he portrays romance and love, by comparing *Happy Together* (1997), to two films that also treat love, being "*Chungking Express*"(1994) and "*In the Mood for Love*"(2000).

3.The universality of Wong Kar-Wai: Love and Romance

When talking about Wong's universality, we refer to the way in which he is able to portray different aspects of love in a way that regardless of the type of relationship you have or you have had in the past, you can identify with it.

Its for his universal approach of love and romance, that we are going to analyze the different perspectives that he brings us, not only in *Happy Together* (1997), but also in two movies that also talk about love, which are *ChungKing Express* (1994) and *In the Mood for Love* (2000)

and by comparing them to our principal study case we will see how Wong Kar-Wai creates this sense of universality that makes this film to follow a more humanist approach, rather than being simply a queer film.

3.1 In the Mood for Love: Love as an ephemeral vapour

In the Mood for Love (2000) tells the story of Chow Mo Wan and Mrs Chan, two neighbours who are cheated upon by their spouses, and they are thrown together by circumstances to find themselves falling in love with each other, instead of their faithless spouses.(Chung, 2013, p.1)

The treatment of love in this movie according to scholar Chin-Yi Chung on her paper “*Wong Kar Wai’s treatment of love in happy together, chungking express and in the mood for love*”(2013), “Wong Kar Wai’s *In the Mood for Love* treats love as an ephemeral vapour, a missed chance and opportunity, a fleeting emotion which never acted upon becomes a ephemeral memory buried by time” (Chung,2013, p.1)

In this movie, love is shown as something that can transcend the physical and the sexual, something that can be evoked principally as a mood the, “love affair” that Mr Chow and Mrs Chan have in the movie, transcend physicality and time, love is presented as an eternal emotion that runs through corridors and rooms, like in the building where they live , being the walls and the temple’s walls of the ending of the movie the ones that burry this love, the relationship between the two of them evaporated, like a kind of vapour or mood and will preserved timelessly (Chung,2013, p.2).

This treatment of love by Wong Kar-Wai is not only present in *In the Mood for Love* (2000), but it is also present in *Happy Together* (1997), not in the relationship between Ho and Fai, but actually in the dynamic that is created later on in the movie between Fai and Chang (Chang Cheng), a taiwanese young man who works in the same restaurant as Fai in Buenos Aires.

The relationship between Chang and Fai appears like a mood or a vapor, it is not the same like the one between Mr Chow (Tony Cheung) and Mrs Chan (Maggie Cheung) in *In the Mood for Love* (2000), but it shares that transcendental aspect of being something more than sexual desire or physical desire, as Fai's feeling for Chang are latent through the movie, he never confesses anything to him as, instead of confessing his true feeling and opening up to him, we get to see Fai's feelings and sadness to be buried into Chang's recorder as not even him will ever know what Fai's true feeling towards Chang where, vanishing through eternity as mere vapour. The difference of this two approaches also relies on the fact that in this case it is only Fai the one that buries his feelings as we never see Chang's sexual interest, making his sexuality and feeling towards Fai as something that are not of any concern (Tambling,2003, p.74)

3.2 ChungKing Express: Love as a rare connection

Chung (2013), describes *ChungKing Express* (1994) as:

“a film about urban alienation and broken relationships, and love as a rare connection that takes place amidst this gloom of social isolation in an urban context. The movie starts with the meditation that we are all strangers to each other in the city, but this may change, people who were once strangers can eventually know each other, and anything may happen from there, including hits and misses in relationships.”
(Chung,2013 p.3)

The movie tells the story of two police officers, Cop 223 (Takeshi Kaneshiro) and Cop 663 (Tony Cheung), as we follow their two parallel stories about their heartbreaks and relationships.

The first character that is presented to us, is Cop 223, who has been left by his girlfriend May, who ended the relationship with him. Cop 223 finds himself lonely and sad, just like Fai in *Happy Together* (1997), he is unable to be alone and has a hard time facing it as:

“the isolation of living in a city and urban setting when relationships turn sour is made clear when Cop 223 turns to calling up his ex-girlfriends and classmates for company, all of whom have either married or have no time for him or do not even remember him.” (Chung,2013, p.3)

Moreover, another interesting aspect of this character is the relationship between him and the pineapple cans, which have an expiration date on his ex-girlfriend's birthday. In this case, Chung (2013), comments that the meditation on relationships as canned pineapples with expiry dates are about the transience of relationships, as we are no different from them when it comes to dating because all relationships have an expiration date when the people we love change and we, or them, decide that we are no longer an interest for them (Chung,2013, p.3). Therefore, we can argue that there is a parallelism between Cop 223 and both, Fai and Ho. When Ho leaves Fai, there is a lack of interest, an expiration date to their relationship and just like canned pineapples their love is slowly consumed the expiration date, when Fai leaves Ho for the first time, therefore ending their romance forever because Fai has changed in that aspect. Moreover, as we argued at the beginning of this paper, *Happy Together*, just like Cop 223, is about loneliness and sorrow as both Ho and Fai are lonely and are unable to move on from the relationship, similar to how Cop 223 struggles to move on from the fact that his girlfriend May will not get back with him.

The second character in this movie is Cop 663, who is left by his girlfriend and then falls in love with a girl who works in a food shop. In the end he is left alone when this girl decides to move to California, leaving Cop 663 alone, similar to Cop 223, Ho and Fai.

ChungKing Express (1994) is a film about the amidst of randomness and anonymity of the city, as Chung (2013) argues:

“(...)strangers we meet being completely random and whom we might or might not develop relationships with which may be transient, there is hope for genuine and deep

connections that might take place over the course of time and with the hope of what was once a random connection developing into deep and beautiful relationships that last over time.”(Chung,2013, p.4)

This same thing happens in *Happy Together* (1997), as the city of Buenos Aires opens itself to many sexual and romantic encounters in the movie. The anonymity of the city serves as an opportunity for Ho to have casual intercourse with strangers and the same is for Fai, when he receives fellatio from a stranger.

In the end, the relationship between Chang and Fai blossoms in the city as it is that through casualty, two strangers meet and share a deep connection for a limited period of time just for it to, in the end, vanish like a mere memory, being all alone in the end.

3.4 The universality of Love

We can conclude that Wong Kar-Wai’s representation of love is a universal feeling of temporality, loneliness, intensity and passion. Love is something that comes and goes, it can be vapor or it can be fire, it is something that in the end will leave a mark on us, whether it is positive or negative.

The universality of his portrayals of love in *In the Mood For Love* (2000), *Happy Together* (1997) or *ChungKing Express* (1994) make a clear distinction that love is the same for everyone and both same sex couples like Ho and Fai or heterosexual couples like Mr Chow and Mrs Chang, can experience the same type of issues, regardless of queerness or not.

For the part of our research, we will analyze the relationship between Ho and Fai and see the dynamic that they both follow throughout the movie.

4. Ho Po-Wing and Lai Yu-Fai: Toxicity, Sadness and Psychoanalysis

For this section, we will construct different meanings of psychoanalytic theory based on both psychologists, Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) and Jacques Lacan (1901-1980).

By this, we will be able to analyze and understand the relationship that both Lai Yu-Fai (Tony Leung) and Ho Po-Wing (Leslie Chung) have, talking about their love, power dynamics and loneliness.

4.1 Freud and Lacan: Oedipus complex and Repetition Compulsion

To construct these meanings of the Oedipus Complex and the Repetition Compulsion, we are going to base our research on scholar Veronica Vega as we will use her paper “*The Oedipus complex in Freud and Lacan*” (2015).

Firstly, we will define what is the “Oedipus complex” for Sigmund Freud, as it is defined as a triangular relationship between the mother, father and kid (Vega,2015,p.5). Moreover, it is described that the kid develops a particular tenderness for her mother, considering her an object, which has to be defended from her father, being in constant dispute with him, at the same time, this also happens with the daughter, who views the mother as a rival and the developing a tender relationship with her father (Freud,1910 as cited in Vega,2015, p.3).

The description of the Oedipus complex in its complete form is for Freud, a way to show the ambivalence that children feel towards their kids, and also on how they develop their heterosexual or homosexual characters, this developments are transmitted later on in life in sexual encounters (Vega,2015, p.3)

Another concept developed by Freud, that will be useful to analyze this relationship, is what he calls the “repetition compulsion”. In Freud’s analysis, scholar Carlos Rojas defines “repetition compulsion is a neurotic condition where in the subject compulsively re-enacts, in symbolic form, the conditions of an earlier, unsolved traumatic event.”(Rojas,2015, p.511)

When talking about the Oedipus Complex, Jacques Lacan adds another layer to it by adding the “phallic figure” to the triangle between kid, mother and father, becoming an element of articulation between the 3 components of the triangle (Vegas,2015, p.5).

For Vegas (2015), Lacan divides the Oedipus complex into 3 phases, being the first one where the kid tries to relate with the object of desire of the mother (phallic figure) creating a full circle relationship between mother and kid where the children is the desired figure and the mother is the one desiring the object (Vegas,2015,p.6).

In the second phase, the father appears as an agent that prevents the mother from its phallic illusion and the kid from the identification with the phallic figure. The father becomes the castrating figure, being a symbol of strength and omnipotence and prevents the mother from closing the relationship with the kid. The figure of the father becomes an object of rivalry for the kid, who now has to fight to be the object of desire of the mother (Vegas,2015,p.7).

The last phase is the ending part of the complex where the kid now needs to be able to recognize the absence of the mother. The father becomes the one that has the “phallic figure” and the kid needs to relates with him (Idea of the self) and the kid transitions from identifying with the phallic figure, to being the beholder of the figure (Vegas,2015,p.8)

The effects of the Oedipus complex for Lacan, are attributed to the possibility of being a subject of desire. This happens, because of the assumption of its own sexuality and self, the imaginary resign of having intercourse with the opposite sex parent, accepting the prohibition of incest and the breaking up of the imaginary relationship between mother and child (Vegas,2015,p.8).

4.2 Lai Yiu-Fai and Ho-Po Wing: Oedipus complex and Repetition Compulsion

Having defined both concepts, we are going to apply the Repetition Compulsion of Sigmund Freud and the Oedipus Complex, developed more deeply by Jacques Lacan, to the characters of Lai Yiu-Fai (Tony Leung) and Ho-Po Wing (Leslie Cheung).

As we mentioned before, the repetition compulsion was about triggering unresolved traumatic events (Rojas,2015, p.511), which in the film are symbolized through the leitmotif

of the movie “Let's start over”, which is said to Fai from Ho to start over their toxic relationship.

The Repetition Compulsion manifests in the cycle of their relationship as both of them try to transform their relationship into something more positive, persisting until there is a point where they split up again therefore igniting the trauma they both carry with the “let's start over”, showing their inability to move on and being stuck in the past, without the ability to live the present or have some direction towards the future (Rojas,2015, p.511).

Rojas (2015) argues that “The result is that the repeated attempts to start over function not only as a mediated re-enactment of an original trauma, but also as a literal extension of that traumatic kernel into the present.”(Rojas,2015, p.511), this means that although they try to have a vision of a future together, their inability and present traumas does not generate a vision of the future, but rather an extended present (Rojas,2015, p.511).

We could conclude from this repetition compulsion, that the relationship between Ho and Fai is primarily utopic, as the two of them cannot have a future together, as they are stuck creating something positive that they cannot succeed because of their traumas, dynamics and personalities therefore being stuck in an extended present.

Moreover, the cycle is finally broken not because they manage to break their recurrence not by fixing their troubled relationship, as it is something impossible, but by recognizing the impossibility of that nominal objective, meaning that it is indeed something that is utopic. (Rojas,2015, p.510)

The breaking of the cycle arrives because of Fai's relationship with Chang as it offered a useful vantage point for Fai, who could have re-evaluated his relationship with Ho because of its relaxed and reciprocal relationship with Chang (Rojas,2015, p.510).

Therefore, the repetition compulsion in the movie is broken by the portrayal that Fai receives from a different point of view, being able to embrace the destructive relationship, creating a new notion of starting over(Rojas,2015, p.515)

In conclusion, Fai “similarly comes to realize that the more he tries to break up with Ho the more susceptible he becomes to Ho’s suggestions that they try to “start over.””(Rojas,2015, p.517)

The Oedipus complex manifests through the power dynamics they both have in the movie as Fai represents the figure of “the mother” as he spends all his energies taking care of a sick Ho, cooking for him and creating a sense of a “controlling mother” by having an obsessive pathology of dependence towards Ho as this is shown in the movie when Fai buys tons of cigarettes to prevent Ho from exiting the apartment and therefore cheating on him again (Chung,2013, p.6).

In the case of Ho, he is wild, promiscuous and abusive, seeking only Fai when he wants sex and runs out of money and also seeking his care and company when he gets beat up for stealing his lovers watch.(Chung 2013, p.5)

Their relationship does not view life as a form of fulfillment, but a means to misery, pathology and dysfunction being Fai the giver and Ho the taker (Chung,2013, p.5), being in this case, Fai the caring mother and Ho the immature child who runs to his mother when things do not go well. Therefore, both of them have a relationship influenced by the Oedipus complex.

Ho sees Fai as a sort of “paternal metaphor” as the notion of phallic power seems, ideologically, a guarantee of stability in relation to the signified (Tanning,2003, p.72), meaning that Ho sees Fai as a paternal and sexual figure, being his safe point when things do not go well for him.

Fai would be the “protective mother” not only because of his endless acceptance of Ho’s abusive behavior , but also because he takes care of him by cooking for him, which is also something that is done because of economic necessity but also because he accepts his role of the “caring mother” that needs to take care of an “immature child”(Tanning,2003).

Being the outcome of this dynamic:

“The result is a deep unhappiness in Yiu Fai. He cares for Po Wing, but cannot accept the constant ill-treatment, abuse, and being taken for granted. He exhausts himself in giving and caring for Po Wing, who is ungrateful and uses him only for sex and when he needs money and care.”(Chung,2013, p.6)

In conclusion, the relationship between Fai and Ho is a utopic relationship in which they are stuck and will never be able to fix because of their traumas and personalities. The dynamic between both of them is destructive and abusive and finally, both of them have a “Oedipal relationship”, meaning that both of them suffer from the Oedipus Complex, creating a paternalistic sexual dynamic between the two of them.

5.Conclusion

As a general conclusion and in terms of queerness, we can argue that *Happy Together* (1997) is not a queer film, not only because Wong Kar-Wai has said multiple times that the film is not a “gay film” (Chung,2013; Tanning,2003; Rojas,2015) but also because the narrative aspect of the film its not the homosexual relationship, but a film about being lonely with someone else (Chung 2013, p.8), it is more about being happy with yourself, with your past (Tanning,2003 p.69).

The protagonists are unable to love because of their inability to transcend themselves, being a doomed relationship, where there is no longer love, but a lack of emotional connection, being the relationship based on dependency and not in love. Fai and Ho need each other not

because they feel genuine love for their partner, but they fear loneliness and they try to find comfort in their company to avoid being alone (Chung,2013, p.8)

Their relationship dynamic is deeply influenced by what we could call an “Oedipal utopic abusive” dynamic (Vegas2015;Rojas,2015), in which they portray paternal roles, both depending on each other for protection and companionship, to avoid the “essential loneliness of the human condition”(Chung,2013, p.8).

The relationship between Ho and Fai is not a queer relationship, but follows a more universal approach, as the point of the movie is not for queer audiences to identify themselves with the movie, but it is done in a way that, it does not matter if you are queer or not, you can identify with the situation that is going on the movie.

In terms of impact, it is this relationship dynamic and the universality achieved by Wong Kar-Wai, that influences Hong Kong’s queer history as, by watching the movie, hetero-normative audiences can engage and feel empathetic to the movie, by feeling the same as if the relationship was heterosexual, this movie could help audiences to realize that queer individuals are the same as them and that, in the end, love is the same for everyone and therefore we should look at love as something that does not distinct from sexual orientation or dynamics. So in conclusion, the movie is not queer in terms of narration or intention but, on social terms the movie is queer because of its universal impact on Hong Kong’s society, giving an opening approach to queerness in a society where the LGBTQ+ collective was not entirely accepted and therefore helping to normalize it.

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